

**Influence of total quality management on human resource management practices- an
exploratory study**

Wickramasinghe, V.

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

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Purpose- This article explores changes occurred in the HR function and HRM practices due to the implementation of TQM in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- Quality managers and HR managers from 77 export-based firms with ISO 9001 certification that have implemented a formal TQM programme and running for at least three years participated in the survey. Factor analysis, correlation and regression were used for the data analysis.

Findings- Firms introduce process improvement initiatives within the HR department by upgrading the role of HR function, and by redesigning HRM practices of performance management, competence development and career planning, rewards and recognition, recruitment and selection, HR planning, and satisfaction and well-being to bring those in line with TQM requirements.

Originality/value- Although quality management literature is extensive, it is difficult to find studies that investigated to what extent TQM practices have been adopted by export-driven organisations in developing economies and what are the changes occurred in the HR function and HRM practices due to TQM initiatives. Understanding these are important to the development of quality management theory in the international context. It is expected that the findings of this exploratory study will be able to establish baseline data to stimulate further research in this area.

Keyword(s): human resource function; human resource practices; quality results; TQM.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

The implementation of quality management techniques enables organisations to improve internal efficiencies, which is considered as a prerequisite to become competitive in global marketplace (Lambert and Ouedraogo, 2008; Stading and Vokurka, 2003). Total quality management (TQM) is an organisation-wide process-oriented philosophy that requires changes not only in production systems, but also in decision-making processes, employee development, and employee participation and involvement (Abdullah et al., 2009; Mehra et al., 2001; Power and Sohal, 2000). The research evidence shows that when organisations

aim towards TQM they adopt more constructive approach to the management of human resources (HR) by upgrading the role of HR function, and redesigning existing human resource management (HRM) practices to fit into quality plans and objectives (Blackburn and Rosen, 1993; Vouzas, 2004). In other words, organisations introduce process improvement initiatives within the HR department in such a way to support strategic aims of quality and to bring it more in line with TQM principles (see Greasley, 2004; Hur 2009; Santos-Vijande and Alvarez-Gonzalez, 2009).

However, existing research has not yet paid the due attention to changes occurred in the HR function and HRM practices as a result of process improvement initiatives undertaken by the HR department due to the implementation of TQM. The main shortcomings of previous empirical studies are that they include a limited number of HRM practices (e.g. recruitment and selection, performance management) in a single study (e.g. Ahmad and Schroeder, 2002; Soltani, 2005, Soltani et al., 2004, 2006). Therefore, it is reasonable to analyze changes occurred in the HR function and HRM practices as a result of the implementation of TQM within a broad framework. Therefore, the current study extends the previous studies by analyzing the influence of TQM on several HRM practices, which until recently had been explored separately, in a single study.

In the above context, this article presents results of the study conducted in Sri Lanka that investigated 1) changes occurred in the HR function due to the implementation of TQM, and 2) changes occurred in HRM practices due to the implementation of TQM. The study focuses to the extent that TQM practices have been adopted by export-driven organizations in developing economies, and the related changes occurred in the HR function and HRM practices.

An understanding of the above aspects is important to the development of quality management theory in the international context (see Gosen et al., 2005; Mandal et al., 2000; Maheshwari and Zhao, 1994; Youssef and Zairi, 1995). The findings of this paper will add knowledge to current TQM practices since the international quality management literature provides little empirical evidence on the influence of TQM practices on HRM. Moreover,

findings will potentially serve as a baseline, and become a source of general guidance in stimulating significant future studies in this area.

Consistent with the objectives, the rest of the paper briefly describes the Sri Lankan context related to the study and reviews the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on the managerial implications of the findings.

Background of the study: Sri Lankan context

The study was conducted among a sample of 77 TQM driven export-apparel manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. The export-apparel manufacturing industry is the leading manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka that has emerged as the country's main export earner and the largest single employment provider in the industrial sector (Department of Census and Statistics, n.d). USA and EU have been Sri Lanka's main apparel importers accounting for over 90 percent of the total value of Sri Lankan apparel exports. When producing apparel for the developed countries in the West, local manufactures have to strictly adhere to product design specifications provided by the foreign buyer, such as Marks and Spencer, who defines product design and quality.

The growth witnessed by this industry can be attributed to two major factors. First, the market-oriented liberal economic policies introduced in 1977 (Fonseka and Fonseka 1998). Second, the Multi-Fibre Agreement (MFA), the worldwide system of managed trade in textiles and apparel that came into existence in 1974, which have been integrated into the WTO framework since 2005. The MFA introduced a quota system for the apparel products' export to developed countries by limiting the quantity of garments that can be exported by the developing countries to any single developed country. Therefore, the aforementioned quota system has been ensured a guaranteed market.

Due to rising wages and quota restrictions by MFA on East Asian economies (such as Hong Kong, South Korea and Taiwan, who were the leaders in apparel export by late

1970s), export-apparel production shifted to Asian quota holding countries, such as Sri Lanka, Thailand, Philippines, Indonesia, China, India, and Pakistan in the late 1970s. Thereafter, the export-apparel production has, further, shifted to other quota holding countries with relatively lower labour cost in Asia (such as Laos, Cambodia, Bangladesh, and Vietnam], Latin and Central America, Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa) (Fonseka and Fonseka 1998, p 255). Overall, under the quota regime, Sri Lanka like other apparel exporting developing countries enjoyed relatively assured export market through bilateral agreements with the developed world.

However, changes occurred when this system of managed trade perpetrated by MFA, came to an end. The World Trade Organisation, which replaced General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) ushered a restriction-free world trade, set out a time period of 10 years from 1995 to 2005 for the phase-out of MFA quota system and the integration of textiles and apparel export trade into the WTO framework. Export-apparel manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka faced this imminent phase-out of MFA quota system for the EU by late 1990s and for the USA (and other Western countries) in 2005. In real terms phasing out of the quota system challenged the very foundation on which this industry had been built. Since the phase-out of the quota system by 2005, apparel exporting countries from Asia, Latin and Central America, Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa have been competing intensively with each other for the market share. Since then, other competitive dimensions such as productivity and quality come on centre stage.

In the meantime, Sri Lankan government declared a decade of productivity improvement from 1997-2006. The principles of Japanese 5-S concept were introduced to both private and public organisations across all sectors, which were encouraged to implement these across the whole organisation as the government initiative involved several Ministries (Central Bank of Sri Lanka 1998). Further, in the year 2001, Sri Lankan government introduced Sri Lanka National Quality Award (SLNQA) programme, which has been formulated in line with the full model of Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) to secure overseas recognition of Sri Lanka's quality capabilities (Tan, 2002).

Thus, an attitudinal change has gradually occurred in the export-apparel manufacturing industry. The former “Q”, i.e., “Quota” driven mentality has been replaced by “Q”, i.e., “Quality” (Saheed 1999, p 29). The change of priorities has influenced the way the industry has been conducting business.

Further, the findings of this study will provide valuable information to both academics and practitioners as it is scarce to find empirical evidence on the influence of TQM on HRM in quality literature, although the export-apparel manufacturing industry counts more than 30 years of development.

Theoretical background

Dimensions of TQM

Quality is no longer confined to the quality of a product or a service; it applies to delivery, administration, customer service, and all other aspects of organisational activities (Tan, 2002). Several authors have developed frameworks to evaluate TQM along the time, which are different in terms of constructs and measurement items (e.g. Ahire et al., 1996; Chen and Lee, 2009; Sun, 2000a). Table 1 maps out the dimensions of TQM commonly proposed in literature. For instance, several researchers have identified the importance of leadership (e.g. Raghunathan et al., 1997; Sun, 2000a; Zhang et al., 2000), supplier relations (e.g. Flynn et al. 1994; Raghunathan et al., 1997; Saraph et al., 1989; Sun, 2000a; Zhang et al., 2000) and human resource processes (e.g. Flynn et al. 1994; Raghunathan et al., 1997; Saraph et al., 1989; Sun, 2000a; Zhang et al., 2000) as dimensions of TQM.

Take in Table 1

Influence of quality system implementation on human resource management practices

Literature suggests the need of process improvement along with quality improvement initiatives (Bendell, 2005; Greasley, 2004). Process improvement is core to various models of quality excellence such as ISO 9001, European Quality Award, Canadian Quality Award, MBNQA and Deming Prize (Bendell, 2005; Stading and Vokurka, 2003). Scholars suggest that process improvement within the HR department is fundamental to organisation-wide structured approach to quality improvement (e.g. Blackburn and Rosen, 1993; Bowen and Lawler, 1992; Soltani et al., 2006; Vouzas, 2004). Organisations that aim towards TQM seem to “adopt more productive and constructive approach to the management of HR by upgrading the role of HR function, redesigning and enhancing the existing HR practices to fit into the quality plans and objectives, providing systematic education and training, relating rewards and recognition to quality and, finally, establishing agreements with trade unions” (see Vouzas, 2004, p126). Overall, TQM initiatives require HR professionals to participate in design, introduction and maintenance of various quality initiatives, re-orient HRM systems to support quality revolution, and establish a quality orientation within the HR function itself (see Bowen and Lawler, 1992; Hart and Schlesinger, 1991; Schoenberger, 1994; Vouzas, 2004).

In the efforts of introducing and implementing quality improvement initiatives, HR departments are challenged to achieve either higher corporate status and greater decision-making authority with more strategic orientation (Palo and Padhi, 2005; Vouzas, 2004) or an outcast, with responsibilities taken over by the line management (Monks et al., 1997). In the context of TQM, the extent to which HR departments undertake and support organisational change efforts have been examined and seriously questioned (Murphy and Southey, 2003; Palo and Padhi, 2005; Soltani et al., 2006; Vouzas, 2004). For instance, Murphy and Southey (2003) suggest that the strategic HR practitioner’s role of the HR function has the potential to be a pro-active agent of change with the ability to develop, plan and implement a wide variety of activities linked to firm performance.

The literature identifies the importance of HRM practices in pursuit of TQM and organisational performance (Dwyer, 2002; Li et al., 2008; Zink, 2008). Several studies found

that organisations introduce or re-design HRM practices, such as human resource planning, recruitment and selection, performance appraisal, rewards and recognition, and human resource development to integrate with TQM expectations (e.g. Ahmad, and Schroeder, 2002; Bou and Beltran, 2005; Hassan et al., 2006; Kanji and Sa, 2003; Monks et al., 1997; Paauwe and Boselie, 2003; Soltani, 2005, Soltani et al., 2004, 2006; Vouzas, 2004; Zairi, 1998). However, it has been also found that many organisations fail to change their HRM systems to meet TQM expectations (Soltani et al., 2004).

However, there is a gap in the literature since the findings were not sufficiently established on changes that may occur in the HR function and HRM practices due to the implementation of TQM. Therefore, given the empirical and anecdotal evidence that indicate TQM dimensions influence the HR function and HRM practices, the current study is expected to show that changes will occur in the HR function and the way HRM practices are performed (namely, human resource planning, recruitment and selection, human resource development, performance appraisal, rewards and recognition, and employee satisfaction and well-being) due to the implementation of TQM.

Methodology

Population, sample selection criteria and sample characteristics

A sample of export-apparel manufacturing firms was identified that fulfilled the following selection criteria set for the study, 1) a firm should be registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) as it is the primary government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating both foreign and local investments in the country and export-apparel manufacturing is the major industrial category under BOI (BOI, n.d.). Further, it is compulsory by law that all BOI-registered firms should export at least 90 percent of the manufactured output (BOI, n.d.). Thus, all export-apparel manufacturing firms that come under this study population are homogeneous in nature in terms of business operations; 2) a firm should have ISO 9001 quality certification. We considered ISO 9001 certification as a starting place on the road to achieving quality orientation. The literature identifies adhering to

ISO 9000 standards represents a sub-system of TQM (Pina and Selle's, 2008; Sun, 2000b). In addition, SLNQA programme which was started in the year 2001 has been formulated in line with the full model of MBNQA (Tan, 2002). Therefore, adhering to ISO 9001 standards represents a sub-system of SLNQA, and 3) a firm should have implemented a formal TQM programme and that should be running for at least three years. This time period was set considering that SLNQA was introduced to the country in 2001 and the total phase-out of MFA quota system occurred in 2005.

Of the 83 firms initially contacted that fulfilled the criteria, 77 firms agreed to participate in the survey. To fulfil the expectations of this study, it was decided to collect data from quality managers and HR managers. The first section of the questionnaire was related to TQM practices, and the second section questioned the influence of TQM practices on the HR function and HRM practices. The instructions required Quality and HR department managers to jointly fill out the survey questionnaire. In the absence of reliable research evidence of quality system performance and the role of the HR department in quality initiatives in Sri Lanka, obtaining information from subject matter experts, namely quality managers and HR managers is considered a good starting point. The data was collected during the first quarter of 2009 and 77 fully completed questionnaires returned.

Respondent firms were from a wide distribution of firm sizes measured in terms of average annual turnover in US\$ and the number of people employed. In terms of average annual turnover (in US\$), 10 percent had less than 0.5 Million average annual turnover, 7 percent had 0.5 to 2 Million, 41 percent had 2 to 10 Million, 38 percent had 10 to 50 Million, 4 percent had 50 to 250 Million. In terms of the number of employees, 23 percent had 100 to 500 employees, 33 percent had 501 to 1000 employees, and 44 percent had over 1001 employees. With regard to the operational time of the HR department, 50 percent declared 1 to 5 years, 10 percent 6 to 10 years, and 40 percent more than 10 years. It was identified that 76 percent of the firms have implemented Worldwide Responsible Apparel Production (WRAP), 42 percent have implemented Ethical Trading Initiatives (ETI) and Global Sourcing

Principles (GSP), and 21 percent have implemented Global Compact (percentages do not add up to 100 due to multiple responses).

Measures

Quality management practices. From the broad range of constituents of quality management (refer to Table 1), The item measures proposed by Raghunathan et al. (1997) for leadership, information and analysis, strategic quality planning, human resource development, quality assurance, supplier relationship, and customer orientation were chosen. The main reasons behind this decision are the following: a) dimensions correspond to MBNQA criteria (see Miyagawa and Yoshida, 2005; Rao et al., 1999; Rughunathan et al. 1997; Sun, 2000a); b) SLNQA programme has been formulated in line with the full model of MBNQA (Tan, 2002), and c) many research conducted in different countries such as the USA, India, Mexico, Norway and China support the content validity and reliability of leadership, information and analysis, strategic quality planning, human resource development, quality assurance, supplier relationship, and customer orientation dimensions of Raghunathan et al. (1997) (see Miyagawa and Yoshida, 2005; Raghunathan et al. 1997; Rao et al., 1999). Each of these dimension was measured using a five-point scale (1=very low, 5 =very high) as used by Raghunathan et al. (1997).

For each measurement scale, standardised Cronbach's alpha (std. α) was applied and principal components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1; loadings should be .50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's standardised alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than .7 (Hair et al., 2006). The factor analysis yielded one factor for each construct, i.e., leadership (std. α =.856; explained variation [EV] =78.83%), information and analysis (std. α =.791; EV=69.75%), strategic quality planning (std. α =.728; EV=64.41%), human resource development (std. α =.891; EV=82.18%), quality assurance (std. α =.752; EV=68.22%), supplier relationship (std. α =.729; EV=62.52%), and customer orientation (std. α =.840; EV=84.74%). The items of

each construct were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct as calculated by Raghunathan et al. (1997) (refer to Table 2).

Changes occurred in the HR function due to the implementation of TQM. Two questions were developed to explore changes occurred in the HR function due to the implementation of TQM. First question was on categorical scale and inquired into whether any changes occurred in the HR function (refer to Table 3). Second question inquired into the nature of changes occurred in the HR function. For this, 6-items were developed and responses were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) (refer to Table 4).

Changes occurred in HRM practices due to the implementation of TQM. A list of changes that could occur in HRM practices due to the implementation of TQM was generated based on preliminary inquiries made during the study and from the literature reviewed earlier. The main HRM practices covered are human resource planning, recruitment and selection, human resource development, performance appraisal, rewards and recognition, and employee satisfaction and well-being. Twenty four items were developed to measure these constructs and these were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). 24-item measure had standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.745. Factor analysis was conducted following the guidelines proposed by Hair et al. (2006), which were detailed earlier. Factor analysis yielded a set of six factors, which explained 84 percent (83.97) of the variance (refer to Table 6). The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct (refer to Table 5).

Results

Correlations of the TQM variables along with means and standard deviations are shown in Table 2.

Take in Table 2

Tables 3 and 4 shows changes occurred in the HR function due to the implementation of TQM. As shown in Table 3, 70 percent of the sample responded that HR activities become more formalised due to the implementation of TQM while 13 percent responded that HR department/unit has been newly established. As shown in Table 4, majority identified that firms are more focused on HRM issues ($\bar{X} = 4.25$), HR function is more closely integrated with business needs ($\bar{X} = 4.12$), and more involved in strategic decision making ($\bar{X} = 3.96$) due to the implementation of TQM.

Take in Table 3

Take in Table 4

Table 5 presents the results of factor analysis showing the changes occurred in HRM practices due to the implementation of TQM. Factor analysis yielded six factors that explained 84 percent of the variance. Factor 1 was labelled as “Performance management”, Factor 2 as “Competence development and career planning”, Factor 3 as “Rewards and recognition”, Factor 4 as “Recruitment and selection”, Factor 5 as “HR planning”, and Factor 6 as “Satisfaction and well-being”. Therefore, results suggest that changes occurred in the way HRM practices were performed due to the implementation of TQM.

Take in Table 5

Discussion and implications

Whilst it is recognised that organisations introduce process improvement initiatives within the HR department to fit into TQM principles, no single study had attempted to investigate changes occurred in the HR function and several HRM practices as a result of process improvement initiatives undertaken by the HR department due to the TQM implementation. Therefore, the findings presented in this article make some contribution to the international quality literature on the influence of TQM practices on HRM.

Being focused on a single industry, which could be identified as the leader in implementing quality management systems in Sri Lanka, ensured a high level of internal validity (Ahire et al., 1996). All the firms in the sample hold ISO 9000 quality certification which visibly demonstrates an organisation's commitment to worldwide quality. Sri Lanka National Quality Award programme that was started in the year 2001 has been formulated in line with the full model of MBNQA. Considering all these circumstances, the firms that implemented a formal TQM programme and running it for at least three years were taken into the sample. We consider all these as strengths of the study. We have used widely accepted multiple parameters drawn from literature to evaluate TQM dimensions. The TQM constructs used in this study were empirically based and shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context. The 24-item measure was developed to explore changes occurred in HRM practices as a result of process improvement initiatives. Factor analysis yielded six components (performance management, competence development and career planning, rewards and recognition, recruitment and selection, human resource planning, and satisfaction and well-being) and these were shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

The study investigated the level of TQM implementation based on the seven dimensions proposed by Raghunathan et al., 1997. These seven dimensions are leadership, information and analysis, strategic quality planning, human resource development, quality assurance, supplier relationship, and customer orientation. Leadership, which is described in terms of personal involvement and visibility in creating goals, values and systems that guide in developing and maintaining an environment of quality excellence is vital in pursuit of

continuous performance improvement (see Raghunathan et al., 1997; Sun 2006; Zhang et al., 2000). Continuous quality improvement relies on a steady flow of accurate information about processes and other constituencies such as employees, suppliers and customers. The importance of effective information usage is well highlighted in the quality literature (see Ahire et al., 1996; Raghunathan et al., 1997; Sun 2006). To achieve world class quality, firms should develop and realise the full potential of the human resource and maintain an environment conducive to participation, quality leadership, and continual updating and improvement of individual and organisational growth. The findings highlight the importance of quality assurance by monitoring processes and systems to maintain the designed quality and make continuous improvements in quality. In the export-led industries like apparel production, quality assurance and customer orientation are key areas for success. When producing apparel targeting developed countries in the West, local manufactures have to strictly adhere to the product design specifications provided by the foreign buyer, who defines product design and quality. It should be noted that the industry's customers are the foreign buyers, such as Marks and Spencer. Hence, customer satisfaction is the key for the survival and growth. The quality management literature also highlights the importance of customer satisfaction identifying it as the ultimate measure of firm performance, which may very well predict the future success or failure of an organisation (see Kanji and Asher, 1993). However, mean values for supplier relationship is also important because when the apparel manufactures receive orders from foreign buyers with product design specifications, suppliers of the clothing materials and accessories and required quality are also specified (mainly materials and accessories are 100% imported as per product design specifications).

One of the main objectives of the study was to explore changes occurred in the HR function and HRM practices as results of the quality improvement efforts. Majority of the firms identified HRM activities has become more formalised due to the implementation of TQM while some responded that HR department/unit has been newly established. Firms have become more focused on HRM issues, more closely integrated with business needs, and more involved in strategic decision making due to TQM initiatives. Some firms identified

a decentralisation of HRM activities to line management and the emergence of a consultancy role for the HR department. This situation is also highlighted in previous quality literature (Psychogios et al., 2009). Overall, firms perceive several changes occurred due to the introduction of quality initiatives and firms have more business-oriented approach to HRM. The literature on quality system implementation also identifies that business process improvement activities due to quality system implementation leads to greater process understanding, ownership and redesign (e.g. Bendell, 2005).

Considerable changes have taken place in the way HRM practices are performed as a result of quality initiatives. The findings led to identify such changes under six broad categories, namely, performance management, competence development and career planning, rewards and recognition, recruitment and selection, human resource planning, and satisfaction and well-being. Overall, the findings imply that the implementation of quality management systems play an important role by altering the HR function, role of HR professionals, and HRM practices, and ultimately, move towards more strategic approach to HRM.

Limitations and future research

There are some limitations in this study. First, data was collected from main persons involved in quality and HR departments as their awareness of quality and HR areas were considered as an advantage. However, the data collection from employees working in quality and HR departments, as well as other employees, would strength the results of the study. Due to scarcity of available previous empirical research investigating the HRM practices explored in this study, we developed item-measures for this study. Therefore, the prevalence of survey instrument related problems have to be acknowledged. However, the validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional exploratory study. Further, the study dealt with seven TQM dimensions and six HRM practices. As the sample size is small (77 firms), structural modelling was not conducted to explore relationships between TQM dimensions and HRM practices. Though the study inquired into

changes occurred in the HR function and practices due to quality system implementation the study has not inquired into tools and techniques used for process improvement. Future studies can investigate those. The nature of organisational change due to the implementation of quality management systems is both continuous and episodic as initial changes are often followed by waves of organisational change that would be political, social, cultural, economic or environmental. As an initial attempt, the study has not explored such changes. Future research could be designed to address such changes.

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Tables

Table 1: Dimensions of TQM proposed in literature

Author(s)	TQM dimensions
Ahire et al. (1996)	Top management commitment; supplier quality management; customer focus; statistical process control usage; benchmarking; internal quality information usage; employee involvement; employee training; design quality management; employee empowerment; product quality.
Flynn et al. (1994)	Top management support; quality information; process management; product design; workforce management; supplier involvement; customer involvement.

Raghunathan et al. (1997)	Leadership; information and analysis; strategic quality planning; human resource development; quality assurance; supplier relationships; customer orientation; quality results.
Saraph et al. (1989)	Role of divisional top management and quality policy; role of quality department; training; product/service design; supplier quality management; process management/operating procedures; quality data and reporting; employee relations.
Sun (2000a)	Leadership; information; strategy; human resources; process; suppliers; business results; customer focus.
Zhang et al. (2000)	Leadership; supplier quality management; vision and plan statement; evaluation; process control and improvement; product design; quality system improvement; employee participation; recognition and reward; education and training; customer focus.

Table 2: Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Leadership	3.64	.41	1					
2. Information and analysis	3.93	.22	.090	1				
3. Strategic quality planning	3.92	.23	.366*	.228	1			
4. Human resource development	3.34	.43	.351*	.031	.068	1		
5. Quality assurance	3.73	.38	.271	.128	.164	.086	1	
6. Supplier relationships	3.90	.24	.203	.181	.329*	.175	.251	1
7. Customer orientation	3.87	.35	.338*	.315*	.328*	.317*	.340*	.247

** significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

* significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

Table 3: Changes occurred in HR function

	%
HR department exists and no major changes occurred to the way organisation manages human resource	16.7
HR department exists and HR activities become more formalised	70.1
HR department/unit has been newly established	13.2
Total	100.0

Table 4: Changes occurred in the activities performed by HR function

	Mean	S.D.
More focused on HRM issues	4.25	.89
HR function is more closely integrated with business needs	4.12	.60
Increased involvement in strategic decision making	3.96	.78
Increased consultancy role of HR department	3.86	.88
HR function is staffed by specialists in the HR area	3.67	.92
Decentralisation of HR activities to line management	3.51	.92

Table 5: Changes occurred in HRM practices due to the implementation of TQM

	Performance management	Competence development and career planning	Rewards and recognition	Recruitment and selection	HR planning	Satisfaction and well-being
Low performers are counselled to improve performance	.874					
Employees are rewarded on the basis of their performance	.860					
Appraisal system has a balance of quantitative and qualitative goals at each job level	.856					
Organisation has formal appraisal systems appropriate to each job level	.846					
Regular feedback is given to employees	.832					
Organisation regularly Identifies training needs		.892				
Organisation has a method of evaluating training and development programmes		.858				
Annual budgetary allocations are made for training and development		.848				
Training programmes are designed for changing organisational requirements		.796				
Career counselling for employees is done regularly		.783				
All employees are aware of their line of promotion		.757				
Employees are educated and aware of rewards and recognition schemes available			.889			
Pay range reflects equity based on employees' work experience and education			.792			
Recognition and rewards effectively stimulate employee performance			.743			
Organisation provides induction programme for all new recruits				.816		
Organisation has clearly focused recruitment and selection process				.804		
HRM procedure manual/employee handbook is available to new recruits				.652		
Job specifications are clearly spelt out for vacant positions				.526		
HR strategies form an integral part of the corporate plan					.854	
Organisation forecasts annual human resources requirements					.758	
Top management has a personal involvement in developing human resource plans					.692	
Exit interviews are conducted						.813
Administers employee satisfaction survey on a regular basis						.777
Administers employee well-being survey on a regular basis						.774
Explained variation	37.07	19.92	11.86	7.03	4.57	3.52
Eigenvalue	5.91	3.73	2.41	2.05	1.94	1.44
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.891	.827	.836	.752	.724	.752
Mean	4.31	3.74	3.55	3.59	3.89	3.15
S.D.	.40	.66	.61	.76	1.03	.94